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Enhancing LoRa-Based Outdoor Localization Accuracy Using Machine Learning

NUR KELEŞOĞLU¹, MARZENA HALAMA², AND ANNA STRZODA³

Institute of Theoretical and Applied Informatics, Polish Academy of Sciences, 44-100 Gliwice, Poland

Corresponding author: Nur Keleşoğlu (nkelesoglu@iitis.pl)

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ABSTRACT The Internet of Things is gaining significant relevance, driving increasing interest in location-based services using wireless signals, particularly Low Power Wide Area Network (LPWAN) technology. LoRa (Long Range), together with LoRaWAN, is a prominent LPWAN standard that provides long-range connectivity and low energy consumption, making it viable for IoT-based positioning systems in smart cities. For localization systems leveraging LoRa signals, Machine Learning (ML) approaches are being increasingly explored, as ML-based solutions offer a powerful way to enhance the accuracy of positioning. In this study, we propose various ML approaches for LoRa-based positioning in outdoor environments. We evaluate six different ML models: k -NN, CNN, SVR, ANN, XG-Boost, and LightGBM using an open-source urban LoRaWAN dataset. We further propose a Hybrid Model that combines convolutional feature extraction with gradient-boosted regression. This architecture integrates the strengths of Deep Learning and tree-based models, aiming to capture both temporal signal patterns and structured input correlations for improved localization accuracy. The models are trained offline and tested for performance in terms of localization accuracy, mean square error, and computational efficiency. Additionally, we investigate the impact of different Feature Vector (FV) subsets on localization performance by analyzing the significance of LoRaWAN signal attributes. Our results highlight the effectiveness of ML models in enhancing localization accuracy for LoRa-based outdoor positioning systems, demonstrating performance improvements ranging from 10% to 73% compared to previous ML studies in outdoor localization.

INDEX TERMS Deep learning, fingerprinting, IoT, k -NN, light GBM, localization, LoRa, LPWAN, machine learning, XG-Boost.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) is transforming industries and urban environments by enabling large-scale, interconnected systems that improve efficiency, automation, and monitoring. As the IoT continues to expand (IoT devices are expected to exceed 34 billion by 2030 [1]), the demand for energy-efficient, scalable, and cost-effective solutions grows. Among the important components of IoT applications is localization, which plays a significant role in domains such as smart

logistics, tracking systems, or location-based services [2], [3]. While a Global Positioning System (GPS) provides accurate positioning in outdoor environments, it is inherently power-intensive, making it unsuitable for many IoT deployments where energy efficiency is a priority. Thus, tracking-based IoT applications using battery-powered devices often require alternative positioning methods that minimize energy consumption, especially as IoT-based smart cities intensify the need for location-based services. LPWAN [4] technologies have emerged as a key enabler, providing long-range connectivity with low-power consumption. LPWAN technologies, including LoRa, Sigfox, MIIoTy (Massive IoT), or

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NB-IoT (Narrowband IoT), are designed to enable low-power radio communication over distances up to a few tens of kilometers at the cost of a low data rate, making them suitable for smart city positioning and tracking systems. While LoRaWAN [5] is among the well-known LPWAN protocols, 6TiSCH (IPv6 over the IEEE 802.15.4e TSCH mode) enables IPv6 connectivity in LPWAN deployments and serves as the basis for standards like Wireless Smart Ubiquitous Network (Wi-SUN). Particularly, in [6], the authors investigated which technology, LoRaWAN or 6TiSCH, performs better in terms of scalability across various scenarios, analyzing metrics such as packet error rate (PER), latency, and node density. They found that LoRaWAN excels in multi-gateway, low-traffic, low-latency deployments, whereas 6TiSCH performs better in high-traffic environments—even though LoRaWAN still offers lower latency under optimal conditions.

LoRa, together with LoRaWAN, as a prominent LPWAN standard, allows battery-powered devices to maintain long-term operation on a single battery (with a lifespan of up to 10 years), providing long-range wireless connections (up to several kilometers), making it widely used in IoT-based smart city applications such as telemetry or remote control [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12]. LoRa operates within the ISM frequency bands - 868 MHz in Europe and 915 MHz in North America. LoRaWAN networks typically are laid out in a star-of-stars topology where one or multiple LoRa gateways facilitate communication between end-devices and the LoRa Network Server. LoRaWAN end devices are designed to be energy-efficient and operate on minimal hardware, often powered by batteries for long-term deployments. Thus, computationally intensive operations are executed on the network's central node, specifically the LoRa Network Server, rather than on the devices themselves. This server is responsible for managing the network infrastructure, coordinating communication with gateways, aggregating data from end devices, and performing signal processing or executing algorithms, such as localization methods.

In LoRaWAN networks, end-device can be located based on its standard uplink transmissions - standard LoRaWAN data packets sent from end-device to the LoRa Network Server via gateways. This means that geolocation does not require any modified or non-standard transmissions, beyond the standard LoRaWAN uplink signals [13]. As a result, LoRaWAN enables positioning without requiring any additional hardware on the end-device beyond the LoRaWAN radio interface. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the development of location-based systems using low-power wide-area signals. The feasibility of using LoRa signals for positioning has been confirmed in numerous previous studies [13], [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [29], [30], [31] for both, indoor and outdoor environments. To achieve increasingly better accuracy, the use of ML methods for localization in LoRa is gaining popularity [32], [33], [34],

[35], [36]. As ML methods continue to gain traction across various domains, their adoption in LoRa networks introduces a promising paradigm shift towards more sophisticated, data-driven localization strategies.

Machine Learning techniques provide flexibility and accuracy beyond conventional methods for localization in LoRa networks, as they can account for multiple factors influencing positioning [37], [38]. ML models can learn complex relationships and variations in signal behavior, such as the variability of the signal in urban and rural areas or NLoS and multipath effects. ML can process large amounts of signal data and draw meaningful conclusions. Conventional methods are not designed to handle such large and complex datasets. ML-based approaches provide significant contributions to location estimation processes in LoRa technology by providing higher accuracy, especially in complex environmental conditions. In this paper, we propose the use of ML models that overcome the limitations of traditional methods for the localization of the end device in LoRaWAN networks. The ongoing need to improve the accuracy of LoRa-based localization using machine learning defines a key research gap, which we address through a consistent comparative analysis of state-of-the-art models. In this study, we train 6 different ML models k -Nearest Neighbors (k -NN), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Support Vector Regression (SVR), Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XG-Boost), and Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM)-offline using an open-source dataset and subsequently test their performance. The results are evaluated in terms of accuracy, mean square error, and computation time. In addition, we compare our findings with previous studies that have used the same dataset. Our study demonstrates an improvement between 10% and 73% in performance over previous work in the context of LoRaWAN technology in outdoor environments.

Additionally, to highlight the significance of the characteristics of the LoRa link, we demonstrated the localization model's average error across different feature sets. We evaluate multiple variants of FV by incorporating both typical signal characteristics, e.g., Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) and additional localization-relevant features, e.g., Signal-to-Noise-Ratio (SNR), Spreading Factor (SF), or Estimated Signal Power (ESP), as well as contextual metadata. We aim to conduct a comprehensive analysis that explores the dataset in depth, taking into account a wide range of FV configurations. This approach allowed us to assess the impact of various features on the model's accuracy, thereby identifying the most crucial attributes for improving positioning performance. By comparing models trained on distinct feature subsets, we were able to systematically analyze the contribution of each feature, ultimately refining the feature selection process to enhance the overall localization accuracy. This analysis underscores the importance of feature engineering and selection in improving the predictive

performance of machine learning models for localization tasks.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: In Section II, we present the state-of-the-art. In Section III, we explain the ML models considered. In Section IV, we explain the publicly available LoRaWAN dataset used in our study, along with the data preprocessing steps applied. In Section V, we present the experimental results. Finally, we conclude the paper in Section VI.

II. RELATED WORKS

The predominant LoRa-based positioning techniques include methods based on signal characteristics, e.g., RSSI and path-loss models, as well as time characteristics, such as Time of Arrival (ToA), Time Difference of Arrival (TDoA), and fingerprinting approaches. The study [39] presents a survey of LoRa-based localization methods as a low-power, GPS-alternative for IoT applications, evaluating techniques like ToA, TDoA, RTT (Round Trip Time), RSSI, and fingerprinting across various real-world scenarios. Semtech [40], a member of LoRa Alliance as well as main provider of LoRa chipsets, has investigated the use of TDoA for geolocation in LoRaWAN infrastructure and reports positioning accuracy between 20 and 200 meters, depending on environmental conditions [13]. However, this approach requires precise clock synchronization, as it relies on differences in signal arrival times, and any timing discrepancies can introduce positioning errors. A TDoA-based localization technique is also employed in [14], demonstrating a median positioning error of less than 500 m. The algorithm was tested using real-world data collected during various mobility scenarios, including driving, cycling, and walking, with a mobile node. Additionally, the same dataset has been utilized to assess the positioning techniques presented in [15]. The study compares the localization accuracy of TDoA and RSSI-based methods within a LoRa network. The findings indicate that the RSSI-based approach yields a significantly higher median localization error of approximately 1 km, whereas the TDoA method achieves nearly tenfold greater precision. The integration of TDoA and Angle of Arrival (AoA) localization within LoRaWAN has been examined in [16] under both Line-of-Sight (LoS) and NLoS conditions, with the most favorable mean positioning error reported at approximately 160 m.

In [17], a LoRa-based localization system employing a TDoA-based multilateration algorithm is presented. Experimental validation in a 6 km² urban area indicates a positioning accuracy of around 100 m. However, the test setup is relatively limited, consisting of a single end node and four LoRa gateways, and the testbed area is more than eight times smaller than the one considered in our study. To enhance localization accuracy in outdoor environments with high noise levels, the study [18] introduces algorithms based on the path-loss model and estimated RSSI error. Experimental results show positioning errors ranging from several meters to several dozen meters over a device

separation of approximately 100 m. Similar findings are reported in [19], where the authors propose RSSI-based localization methods aimed at mitigating noise effects in LoRa networks for both outdoor and indoor environments. Yoshitome et al. [41] evaluated a LoRa-based outdoor localization system utilizing RSSI and TDoA techniques for localization over a 4 km² area. The results showed that while TDoA generally outperforms RSSI in accuracy, with localization errors ranging from 66 to 253 meters, it requires precise synchronization between anchors, making RSSI a simpler but less accurate alternative.

The feasibility of LoRa for indoor and outdoor positioning is further explored in [20], where Wiener filters are applied to reduce RSSI measurement noise in a trilateration-based localization approach. The most optimistic mean localization error is under 500 m in an urban area of 0.5 km², and 20-30 meters in indoor environments. The effectiveness of the proposed approach has been evaluated using the dataset from [21]. The main limitation of these studies is that they do not investigate the performance of the location system in real-life conditions. They offer a limited analysis of link characteristics and the variability of signal attenuation. While city-wide deployments are often considered, most studies include only a small number of gateways (sometimes as few as four [17]).

Nevertheless, the studies [22], [42] present the results of LoRa positioning system accuracy gathered in a real-life, large-scale telemetry network. However, the network coverage area from this study covers a 20% smaller area compared to the dataset in the study [43], which we consider in our work. Moreover, the authors do not provide open access to the dataset investigated in their study and do not consider ML-powered approaches for LoRa positioning. The authors apply a trilateration technique, which has been shown to provide location estimation with a median error of 588 m and an average error equal to 808 m.

The study [23] presents an RSSI fingerprinting technique based on hi-res satellite images from the Deep Globe dataset [24] for position estimation. The authors use the method of linear and RBF interpolation, using maximum likelihood estimation (MLE). The experiments were conducted in a small-scale test environment of 0.1 km² with only four LoRa gateways, which limits its applicability to larger deployments. The method achieved a mean localization error of 28.8 m, with the best accuracy recorded at 24 m.

Regarding ML-based estimation techniques, recent studies demonstrate the application of machine learning methods for positioning in LoRaWAN networks. One of the latest studies [32] proposed RSSI-based offline training and online phase for localization of devices in LoRaWAN network by performing k -NN and Neural Network ML models. The study uses the publicly available LoRaWAN dataset [43] and applies two different normalizations to the features, exponential and power, and presents the results. The k -NN model achieved the best performance with Power normalization, resulting in a mean error of 313.26 m.

Similarly, the Neural Network model yielded the lowest mean error of 277.61 m using Power normalization. The study [33] presents an indoor localization method based on LoRaWAN and RSSI fingerprinting, utilizing neural network-based ML algorithms to classify room sectors achieving the accuracy of up to 94.54% across multiple scenarios divided into 256 sectors. The recent study [35] introduces another RSSI-based fingerprint localization method for LoRaWAN using branched CNNs enhanced with squeeze-and-excitation blocks. The model achieved a mean localization error of 284.57 m on the same public dataset, which we consider in our work.

The study [44] localizes IoT devices in LPWAN based on a machine learning fingerprinting algorithm and range-based localization algorithm by using RSSI values from publicly available dataset [43]. Ten different ML regression models were used, including SVR, k -NN, Random Forest (RF), and linear regression with different variances for estimating the position of the IoT device. The study presented three different normalization methods: lineal, Exponential, and Powed. The SVR model with lineal scaling had a mean error of 1148 meters. The k -NN model with weighted Powed scaling yielded a mean error of 343 m, while the RF model with Powed RSSI achieved a mean error of 340 m. The error values for linear regression and its variations ranged between 784 and 801 meters. The performance of the range-based localization algorithm in terms of mean square error varies between 700-1687 meters for different path-loss models. In another study [37] using the same dataset, the RF model was applied by proposing range-based localization, and a localization accuracy of 735.37 m was obtained, which is approximately three times larger than what we achieved.

The studies above show the feasibility of using both conventional localization techniques and ML-based approaches in LoRa networks across indoor and outdoor environments and testbeds of various scales. While previous studies have shown the potential of machine learning in LoRa-based localization, enhancing the accuracy of these methods remains a central focus in ongoing research. Given the growing potential of machine learning in location-based systems utilizing LoRa signals, along with the technology's long-range capabilities, we investigate the performance of ML-powered approaches for outdoor localization with LoRa.

III. MACHINE LEARNING BASED DEVICE LOCALIZATION IN LORA NETWORK

In this section, we present the overall methodology of our proposed RSSI-based outdoor localization framework in LoRaWAN networks, as illustrated in Figure 1. The process begins with the preprocessing stage, where meta data is first processed to extract relevant signal features such as RSSI values. Extracted features form input vectors, with optimal parameters tuned on RSSI-based training data. In the model training phase, seven different Machine Learning algorithms, k -NN, CNN, SVR, ANN, XGBoost, LightGBM,

and a Hybrid Model are trained on the constructed FV. To further enhance localization accuracy and address the lack of architectural novelty, we introduce a hybrid regression model that integrates CNN-based feature extraction with XGBoost-based regression. This architecture leverages the representational strength of Deep Learning and the robustness and interpretability of gradient boosting methods.

After training, all models—including the proposed Hybrid Model—are evaluated on the test dataset. Each model produces predicted GPS coordinates (y_{lat} , y_{lon}), allowing for a comprehensive comparison of localization performance and inference efficiency. To ensure reproducibility, the code for all model architectures is publicly available via our GitHub repository at [45].

The input data was constructed from RSSI values measured at multiple gateways during packet transmission over a LoRaWAN network. Initially all models were trained using only RSSI values to determine the optimal hyperparameters and to understand the contribution of RSSI itself. Afterwards, the input dataset was extended with additional features described in Section IV. For each sample $i \in [1, \dots, m]$, the RSSI values received from all gateways are collected into a single input vector:

$$X_{RSSI}[i] = [x_{RSSI,1}[i], \dots, x_{RSSI,G}[i]] \in \mathbb{R}^G. \quad (1)$$

Here, $x_{RSSI,g}[i]$ denotes the RSSI measured by gateway $g \in [1, 2, \dots, G]$ for the i -th packet.

A. K -NEAREST NEIGHBORS

The k -NN algorithm is a non-parametric method used in our study to estimate location coordinates based on RSSI measurements. Rather than training a global model, it predicts the position of a test sample by averaging the coordinates of the k most similar training samples [46]. Similarity is computed using either Minkowski distance (with $p = 1$ for Manhattan, $p = 2$ for Euclidean, and $p = 3$ for Chebyshev) or Cosine Similarity.

The k most similar samples, $\mathcal{N}_k(X_{RSSI}[j])$, are selected based on the chosen metric, and their target values (coordinates) are averaged to predict the final position. This flexibility allows the algorithm to adapt to varying characteristics of the RSSI signal space.

B. CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS

CNNs are used in our study to extract spatial patterns from RSSI vectors for device localization [47], [48], leveraging their ability to hierarchically learn features relevant for accurate coordinate prediction directly from raw RSSI data without manual feature design.

A 1D convolution is applied to X_{RSSI} with a learnable filter $W \in \mathbb{R}^k$, producing the feature map Y :

$$Y_i = \sum_{u=1}^k W_u \cdot X_{RSSI}[i + u - 1]. \quad (2)$$

FIGURE 1. General architecture of the proposed methodology, illustrating the preprocessing stage, model training phase, and position estimation process.

Convolutional and pooling layers are followed by fully connected layers that produce the final location estimate. A dense layer neuron output is:

$$h_j = f \left(\sum_{g=1}^G w_{k,g} x_{RSSI,g}[i] + b_k \right), \quad (3)$$

where $w_{k,g}$ are the weights, $x_{RSSI,g}[i]$ are the inputs from the previous layer, b_k is the bias term, and $f(\cdot)$ is an activation function.

C. SUPPORT VECTOR REGRESSION

Support Vector Regression (SVR) is used in our study to estimate continuous location coordinates from RSSI vectors [49]. Based on the maximum margin principle, SVR fits a function within an ϵ -tolerance margin of the true values.

The ϵ -insensitive loss is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_\epsilon(y_i, \hat{y}_i) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \leq \epsilon \\ |y_i - \hat{y}_i| - \epsilon, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

To handle nonlinear patterns, we use kernels such as linear, polynomial, RBF, and sigmoid. The SVR prediction function is:

$$\hat{y}_i = \sum_{j=1}^m \alpha_j K(x_{RSSI}[j], x_{RSSI}[i]) + b, \quad (5)$$

SVR is applied separately to estimate latitude and longitude, offering a flexible regression approach for RSSI-based localization.

D. ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are used in our study to estimate device location in a LoRaWAN environment [50]. They consist of interconnected layers of neurons that transform input features through learned weights and nonlinear activation functions. The output of each neuron is computed as in Equation (3), enabling the model to capture complex relationships in RSSI data. We use a feedforward ANN with dense layers to predict continuous coordinates. This structure allows the model to learn a mapping from RSSI input vectors to spatial positions without requiring manual feature design.

E. EXTREME GRADIENT BOOSTING

Extreme Gradient Boosting (XG-Boost) is a decision tree-based ensemble model known for its high predictive accuracy and efficiency [51]. In our study, it is applied to RSSI input vectors for location estimation. Each RSSI input $X_{RSSI}[i]$ is processed through an ensemble of trees to generate a final prediction \hat{y}_i . This approach balances speed, accuracy, and overfitting resistance in the localization task.

F. LIGHT GRADIENT BOOSTING MACHINE

LightGBM is a gradient boosting framework that builds decision trees efficiently using histogram-based algorithms and leaf-wise tree growth [52]. In our study, it is applied to predict location coordinates from RSSI vectors.

The model performs regression by combining outputs of multiple trees:

$$\hat{y}_i = \sum_{k=1}^K f_k(\mathbf{x}_{RSSI}[i]), \quad f_k \in \mathcal{F}, \quad (6)$$

where \mathcal{F} is the set of regression trees. LightGBM offers fast training and low memory usage while maintaining high accuracy in RSSI-based localization. As in SVR, we train separate models for latitude and longitude prediction.

G. HYBRID MODEL

In this study, we propose a Hybrid Model that integrates a CNN with an XGBoost regressor to leverage the representational capacity of Deep Learning and the decision-making effectiveness of tree-based models. The model is designed to enhance localization accuracy by extracting latent patterns from features and incorporating them as additional inputs.

The mathematical description of the model when only RSSI values are used as features is as follows. As introduced in Equation (1), each input sample $i \in [1, \dots, m]$ is represented by a vector of RSSI values measured at G gateways.

To capture temporal dependencies and local spatial patterns in the signal strength data, a one-dimensional CNN is applied over a temporal window of RSSI measurements. Let $\mathbf{X}[i] \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times G}$ represent a time-ordered matrix of RSSI values for sample i , where T is the window length and G is the

number of gateways. The CNN acts as a feature extraction function Φ_{CNN} , defined as:

$$\mathbf{z}[i] = \Phi_{\text{CNN}}(\mathbf{X}[i]) = \text{Flatten}(\sigma(\mathbf{X}[i] * \mathbf{W} + \mathbf{b})), \quad (7)$$

where $*$ denotes the convolution operation, \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{b} are learnable filter weights and biases, and σ is a non-linear activation function such as ReLU. The output $\mathbf{z}[i] \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is a high-level feature embedding capturing signal structure over time.

Next, the embedding $\mathbf{z}[i]$ is concatenated with the original static input vector $X_{\text{RSSI}}[i]$ and other derived features (as described in Section IV) to form an extended FV:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}[i] = [X_{\text{RSSI}}[i]; \mathbf{f}_{\text{extra}}[i]; \mathbf{z}[i]] \in \mathbb{R}^{p+d}, \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{f}_{\text{extra}}[i]$ contains engineered features such as SNR, ESP, or timestamp-based statistics, and p is the total dimensionality of handcrafted features.

This composite vector $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}[i]$ is then used as input to an XGBoost regressor f_{XGB} , which learns to predict the coordinates of the packet source:

$$(\hat{y}_1[i], \hat{y}_2[i]) = f_{\text{XGB}}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}[i]), \quad (9)$$

where \hat{y}_1 and \hat{y}_2 represent the estimated latitude and longitude of sample i .

XGBoost minimizes a regularized objective function overall m training samples:

$$\mathcal{L} = \sum_{i=1}^m \ell(\mathbf{y}[i], \hat{\mathbf{y}}[i]) + \sum_{k=1}^K \Omega(f_k), \quad (10)$$

where $\ell(\cdot)$ is the loss function (e.g., mean squared error), f_k denotes the k -th regression tree in the ensemble, and $\Omega(f_k)$ is a regularization term penalizing tree complexity. As the FV evolve depending on the dataset, the input to the CNN also changes accordingly. Therefore, the set of features extracted by the CNN may differ across datasets, depending on which signal indicators (e.g., RSSI, SNR, ESP) are available and selected.

The proposed hybrid architecture thus offers a principled integration of learned and handcrafted features by combining temporal feature extraction via CNNs with the structured regression capabilities of XGBoost. This design aims to capture both local signal dynamics and global feature correlations in a complementary manner. By leveraging the strengths of both Deep Learning and gradient boosting, the Hybrid Model establishes a versatile and extensible framework for RSSI-based outdoor localization.

IV. DATASET

In this study, we use the latest open-source version of the LoRaWAN dataset from ‘‘Sigfox and LoRaWAN datasets for fingerprint localization in large urban and rural areas’’ [43], which was created for fingerprint localization algorithms in wide outdoor areas (52.97 km²). The dataset inherently reflects the complexities of real-world deployments, having been collected under diverse topographic conditions, in the

presence of physical obstructions, and across both LoS and NLoS scenarios. These factors introduce signal degradation effects such as shadowing, reflection, and multipath propagation, which are essential for evaluating localization robustness. Furthermore, the use of mobile sensors during data collection enables a more realistic assessment of model performance under dynamic conditions. Regarding these factors, e.g., RSSI—a signal feature commonly used for localization but inherently sensitive to environmental conditions—tends to exhibit significant noise under such propagation conditions. Therefore, it is essential to consider additional characteristics related to propagation conditions (e.g., SNR, SF) beyond RSSI, which we incorporate into our approach to enhance positioning accuracy.

Measurements for the dataset were collected over several months in various urban and rural areas, including signal characteristics such as RSSI, along with the GPS coordinates of the transceivers. The LoRaWAN dataset contains 123, 529 messages collected in Antwerp, Belgium, from 17 November 2017 to 5 February 2018. Twenty Antwerp postal service vehicles and Firefly X1 GPS receivers were used to collect the dataset. Postal service vehicles’ positions (latitude, longitude) and GPS signal quality known as Horizontal Dilution of Precision (HDOP), were continuously recorded and transmitted to gateways as LoRaWAN messages via IM880B-L radio modules each minute. In the first version of the dataset, there are 68 gateways. However, we used the latest version (ver. 1.3) of the ‘lorawan_dataset_antwerp’ dataset since we focused on outdoor device localization in the Lora network. The latest version was released in 19 July 2019 and included 72 gateways and around 130, 429 LoRaWAN messages. The Figure 2 shows the GPS coordinates corresponding to the locations, visualized on a map created using Google My Maps. Due to platform limitations, only approximately 40% of the data points (around 52, 172) are displayed.

FIGURE 2. Illustration of the dataset related to LoRaWAN signal reception across various locations, based on GPS coordinates.

In this version, the dataset is published in both CSV and JSON formats. The CSV format includes information such as HDOP, RSSI, and the Spreading Factor (SF) - parameter related to propagation conditions, while the JSON format contains a more comprehensive metadata array. Some

attributes in the dataset such as ‘dev_addr’, ‘dev_eui’, ‘payload’, ‘adr’, ‘ts_type’, and ‘time’, were not utilized for localization purposes. The primary reason for excluding these features is their lack of direct relevance to the position estimation process. For instance, ‘dev_addr’ and ‘dev_eui’ are device identifiers specific to the LoRaWAN network but do not contribute to signal propagation characteristics or geographical positioning. Similarly, ‘payload’ carries application-specific data unrelated to localization. Also, ‘adr’, adaptive data rate, is a network optimization parameter that does not provide spatial information. Additionally, ‘ts_type’ and ‘time’ are timestamp attributes, and they do not provide additional position information.

We create multiple Feature Vector subsets, each containing a distinct selection of relevant attributes to evaluate the impact of different FV on the localization accuracy. However, before performing, we implement a data preprocessing stage. It allows for handling missing values and normalizing numerical features.

Although the dataset references 72 gateways and the CSV file includes ‘RSSI’ values for all 72, messages were received by only 44 gateways. Consequently, when reading the data from the JSON format, we access only 44 ‘gateway IDs’. The ‘latitude’ and ‘longitude’ attributes represent the GPS coordinates of the transmitting device, serving as the outputs for machine learning models in the localization process.

Due to the large number of samples (messages in this dataset) and gateways in the dataset, applying data preprocessing is essential before implementing the ML models. Additionally, the number of gateways and the number of messages received by these gateways play a significant role in ML-based localization. We apply the following preprocessing stages to the dataset to achieve optimal performance from the ML models, reduce the distance between the actual (ground truth) and predicted locations, and enhance localization accuracy.

First, we processed the dataset by reading the JSON format and structuring it so that each message corresponds to a single sample, with features represented as columns. Since not all gateways receive every transmitted message, missing RSSI values were assigned a placeholder value of -200 dBm, as also reflected in the CSV file. After this transformation, the final dataset consisted of 130,430 samples, which were then saved as a CSV file for further analysis.

Second, we determined the range of RSSI values in the dataset between -127 dBm and -60 dBm. In addition, -200 dBm was placed instead of the NaN value in the dataset when no messages were received. There is no value between -200 dBm and -127 dBm. The outlier values in the dataset -200 dBm may affect the performance of machine learning models. To address this problem, we replaced all the -200 dBm values with the neighboring value, i.e., one less than the smallest value -128 dBm, as implemented in the study [32]. Thus, the new RSSI range is -128 dBm to -60 dBm. Although missing values could be addressed using alternative approaches, which is a worthwhile direction for

future research, in our work, we rely on a methodology that is well-established in the previous studies utilizing the same dataset [32].

The last step is the normalization of the data. RSSI values are measured logarithmically as follows

$$P_{dBm} = 10 \log_{10} P_{mW}, \quad (11)$$

where P_{dBm} is the signal strength in dBm, and P_{mW} is the signal strength in milliwatts. Due to the logarithmic nature of RSSI, the power actually decreases by a factor of 10 for every 10 dB decrease in signal strength. Therefore, it is not appropriate to use linear normalization to normalize RSSI values. Thus, we apply a logarithmic transform to the RSSI values. The following formula illustrates how each value is transformed using a logarithmic transformation:

$$\hat{X}_{RSSI,g}[i] = \log_{10}(|X_{RSSI,g}[i]| + 1), \quad (12)$$

where $X_{RSSI,g}$ represents a column of RSSI values transmitted to the g gateway in the data and $g \in [1, 44]$. The i represents any sample in the dataset. This transformation helps to normalize the RSSI distribution, reducing the impact of extreme values and improving the performance of ML models. After logarithmic transformation, we apply min-max normalization and scale RSSI values between 0 and 1. The following formula represents the normalization of logarithmically transformed RSSI values:

$$\bar{X}_{RSSI,g}[i] = \frac{\hat{X}_{RSSI,g}[i] - \min(\hat{X}_{RSSI})}{\max(\hat{X}_{RSSI}) - \min(\hat{X}_{RSSI})}. \quad (13)$$

The other features of the dataset, except the RSSI values and the output variables, were grouped under the name X_{other} . This category includes attributes such as SF, SNR, ESP, channel information, counter, and airtime. Normalization of the features in this group was performed by min-max scaling within itself. The formula below shows the normalization of the features in this group.

$$\bar{X}_{other,j}[i] = \frac{X_{other,j}[i] - \min(X_{other,j})}{\max(X_{other,j}) - \min(X_{other,j})}, \quad (14)$$

where j represents a feature, and each $X_{other,j}$ represents a feature column from the dataset. Finally, in machine learning, the input data is represented as X and is formalized as follows:

$$X = [\bar{X}_{RSSI}, \bar{X}_{other}]. \quad (15)$$

This formulation ensures a clear distinction between signal strength features and other relevant input parameters used in the localization model. In addition, we applied min-max normalization to the target variables, scaling the values between 0 and 1. The latitude target is represented as y_{lat} , and the longitude target is represented as y_{lon} . For machine learning models, the output y is formalized as follows:

$$y = [y_{lat}, y_{lon}]. \quad (16)$$

This normalization ensures that the output values are within a standardized range, improving model stability and convergence during training.

V. RESULTS

We present our results in five categories. In Section V-A, we present the localization performance of benchmarking ML models in various evaluation metrics. In Section V-B, we provided a performance comparison of the model based on different feature sets. We present the localization accuracy in Section V-C. We show the location estimation error in Section V-D in terms of meters, and we provide the computation time of ML models in Section V-E. The machine learning models were implemented using Python, with the TensorFlow (Keras) and Scikit-learn libraries employed for model development, training, and testing.

A. PERFORMANCE OF MACHINE LEARNING MODELS

This subsection presents the performance of the comparative ML models that we applied to estimate device location using only RSSI data received by the gateways in the LoRaWAN network. The primary reason for using only RSSI data is to observe the performance of the models based on RSSI input and to identify the optimal hyperparameters for each model. The subsequent part of the paper examines the impact of additional features on the localization error and presents the computation time of ML models.

As we mentioned in Section III, we applied six different ML models: k -NN, CNN, SVR, ANN, XG-Boost, and LightGBM for outdoor device location estimation in LoRaWAN networks. Additionally, a Hybrid Model combining CNN-based feature extraction with XGBoost regression was implemented to further improve localization accuracy by leveraging complementary strengths of both methods. For each model, 70% (91,300 samples) of the dataset were used for training, 15% (19,564 samples) of the data were used as validation data, and 15% (19,565 samples) data were used for testing. The train, validation, and test samples are the same for each model. Grid search was applied to select hyperparameters for each model, and the results were presented with the appropriate metric for each model. The hyperparameters that provided the best performance were selected, and the models were trained. In the rest of the subsection, the usage of each model, its hyperparameters, and performance calculation metrics are explained in detail.

To quantitatively evaluate the effectiveness of the models, several key performance metrics were used: the coefficient of determination (R^2 score), Mean Squared Error (MSE), Median Error (ME), Standard Deviation (SD), and computational efficiency.

R^2 score is a statistical measure that shows how well the regression models fit. It is commonly used as an evaluation metric in regression models. The mathematical formulation of the R^2 score is shown in (17) where $SS_{regression}$ and SS_{total} are the residual sum of squared error and total error sum of squares respectively.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{SS_{regression}}{SS_{total}}. \quad (17)$$

Equation 18 shows R^2 score in detail where y_i , \hat{y} , and \bar{y} are actual value, predicted value, average of actual values respectively.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum (y_i - \hat{y})^2}{\sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2}. \quad (18)$$

The R^2 score measures how well a regression model predicts actual values, ranging from 0 to 1. A score of 1 indicates perfect predictions, 0 means no predictive power, and values below 0 imply worse performance than simply using the mean. The MSE is a standard metric used to measure the average squared difference between predicted and actual values. It is defined as:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2. \quad (19)$$

A lower MSE indicates better model performance, as it reflects smaller prediction errors. An MSE of 0 means the model's predictions are perfectly accurate.

ME is the middle value of all prediction errors when sorted. It is less sensitive to outliers than the mean and provides a robust estimate of typical error.

SD measures the spread of prediction errors around the mean error. A lower SD means predictions are more consistent. The general mathematical formula is as follows:

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (|y_i - \hat{y}_i| - MSE)^2}. \quad (20)$$

1) K -NN

The k -NN method can be optimized by selecting two crucial parameters: k , which determines the number of nearest neighbors, and p , which determines the distance metric, which defines how distances between points are calculated. In our experiment, we evaluated four different distance metrics: Manhattan, Euclidean, Chebyshev, and Cosine similarity. Specifically, Manhattan and Euclidean distances correspond to $p = 1$ and $p = 2$ in the Minkowski family, while Chebyshev distance uses $p = \infty$. Cosine similarity, although not a Minkowski distance, is widely used for its effectiveness in high-dimensional spaces. Depending on the choice of these parameters, the performance of the k -NN model varies in terms of accuracy and robustness. The results for different k values and distance metrics are presented in Table 1. In this part of our experiment, we tested with a number of hyperparameter configurations, in particular using $k = [5, 7, 9, 11]$ combined with all four distance metrics to assess their impact on model performance.

The performance of the k -NN model on the test data for the best hyperparameter values ($p = 1$ and $k = 11$) is quantified by the R^2 score, which equals 0.9147. As shown in Table 1, the corresponding mean error is 338.56 meters.

2) CNN

We evaluated the performance of a 1D-CNN for localization using RSSI strength index measurements. The network

TABLE 1. Average localization error of the k -NN model for different values of k using different similarity measures.

Distance Metric	k Value	Mean Error	Median Error	Standard Deviation
Cosine	3	381.90 m	225.81 m	464.90 m
	5	363.08 m	226.88 m	436.90 m
	7	360.23 m	222.54 m	431.54 m
	11	352.74 m	218.09 m	425.93 m
Manhattan	3	360.26 m	207.13 m	454.98 m
	5	347.36 m	208.86 m	431.68 m
	7	342.62 m	206.95 m	424.53 m
	11	338.56 m	209.15 m	417.30 m
Euclidean	3	362.53 m	209.65 m	455.21 m
	5	349.98 m	212.83 m	432.29 m
	7	344.50 m	210.75 m	423.90 m
	11	340.75 m	211.01 m	418.19 m
Chebyshev	3	371.10 m	214.75 m	461.65 m
	5	358.65 m	218.89 m	437.91 m
	7	354.39 m	216.76 m	429.31 m
	11	350.40 m	216.57 m	424.24 m

architecture was kept consistent across all experimental trials, while key hyperparameters were varied, including the learning rate set to 0.001 and 0.005, and the number of training epochs set to 10, 50, 100, and 200.

The proposed network consists of 2 convolutional layers with 32 and 64 filters, respectively, with a kernel size of 3 and a ReLU activation function. Once the feature extraction process is complete, the data are flattened and transferred to a fully connected (dense) layer containing 128 neurons. In order to reduce the risk of overfitting the model, a dropout regularisation layer was used with a neuron exclusion probability of $p = 0.2$. The final layer is a dense layer with linear activation that outputs two geographical coordinates, and the network was trained using the Adam optimizer.

For the optimal hyperparameters (learning rate = 0.001 and epochs = 200), the CNN model achieved an R^2 score of 0.907 on the test data. As shown in Table 2, the corresponding mean error was 338.78 meters. However, for further analysis and model evaluation, the number of training epochs was limited to 100. This decision aimed to reduce the risk of overfitting, as the model had already shown stable and satisfactory performance. Moreover, gains beyond

TABLE 2. Average localization error of CNN model for different learning rates and numbers of training epochs.

Learning Rate	Epochs	Mean Error	Median Error	Standard Deviation
0.001	10	381.22 m	278.16 m	386.25 m
	50	342.48 m	240.19 m	374.76 m
	100	343.88 m	234.16 m	380.84 m
	150	341.38 m	227.98 m	368.68 m
	200	338.78 m	229.21 m	372.25 m
0.005	10	410.99 m	322.34 m	397.31 m
	50	392.39 m	278.26 m	385.64 m
	100	355.41 m	243.01 m	369.84 m
	150	351.74 m	245.78 m	373.69 m
	200	346.17 m	280.99 m	364.72 m

100 epochs were marginal, while training time increased significantly.

Additionally, a separate set of experiments was conducted to investigate the impact of convolutional filter size and kernel configuration on localization performance (see Table 3).

TABLE 3. Average localization error of CNN models under various filter and kernel configurations.

Filters		Kernel Sizes		Error Metrics		
1	2	1	2	Mean Error	Median Error	Standard Deviation
32	64	3	3	350.23 m	240.83 m	384.15 m
16	32	3	3	355.42 m	246.02 m	378.29 m
64	128	3	3	346.71 m	237.29 m	385.09 m
32	64	5	5	351.98 m	245.34 m	385.09 m
32	64	7	7	362.70 m	243.19 m	374.70 m
64	128	2	2	357.68 m	235.57 m	371.90 m
32	64	2	2	345.06 m	235.75 m	370.94 m
16	32	5	5	356.29 m	249.65 m	378.99 m

Eight Conv1D layer configurations were tested by varying filter counts and kernel sizes, with other network components fixed. The best model (64 and 128 filters, kernel size 3) achieved a mean error of 346.71 m and a median of 237.29 m,

suggesting that adjusting convolutional layers can moderately improve prediction accuracy.

3) SVR

We applied SVR for device location estimation, where the location is defined by two coordinates: latitude and longitude. Since SVR inherently performs regression with a single output, we develop two separate SVR models, one for predicting latitude, SVR-LAT, and the other for predicting longitude, SVR-LON. Each model undergoes hyperparameters such as regularization parameter C and ϵ tuning using grid search, and the results are evaluated based on the R^2 score. The model achieving the highest R^2 score is selected and saved for device location prediction. The kernel type, hyperparameters, and corresponding R^2 scores for both SVR models are presented in Table 4.

TABLE 4. R^2 Scores of SVR models evaluated across various kernel types and hyperparameter settings.

Model	Kernel	Parameters					
		C	ϵ				
			0.01	0.04	0.1	0.2	0.3
SVR-LAT	Linear	0.05	0.8179	0.8197	0.8219	0.8107	0.7698
		0.1	0.8179	0.8197	0.8219	0.8106	0.7736
		0.2	0.8179	0.8196	0.8219	0.8107	0.7750
		0.3	0.8179	0.8196	0.8219	0.8108	0.7751
	RBF	0.05	0.9469	0.9452	0.9320	0.8968	0.6890
		0.1	0.9480	0.9463	0.9340	0.9017	0.7414
		0.2	0.9486	0.9471	0.9357	0.8982	0.7756
		0.3	0.9488	0.9474	0.9365	0.8961	0.7889
SVR-LON	Linear	0.05	0.7038	0.705	0.6866	0.5635	0.1756
		0.1	0.7039	0.7058	0.6864	0.5936	0.1903
		0.2	0.7037	0.7058	0.6864	0.6143	0.1922
		0.3	0.7037	0.7057	0.6863	0.6250	0.2244
	RBF	0.05	0.8857	0.8782	0.8499	0.7329	0.2709
		0.1	0.8890	0.8824	0.8514	0.7662	0.3669
		0.2	0.8912	0.8852	0.8519	0.7800	0.4204
		0.3	0.8918	0.8855	0.8491	0.7683	0.4620

Table 4 presents the R^2 scores of models trained with the same dataset for different kernels in both SVR models (SVR-LAT and SVR-LON). The regularization parameter C takes values from [0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3], while ϵ is set to [0.01, 0.04, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3]. The bold values highlight the top performance of both models. These results indicate that the

highest model performance was obtained using the RBF kernel, with a regularization parameter C of 0.3 and ϵ of 0.01. Using these optimal hyperparameters, the average localization error in the test dataset was 331.92 meters.

4) ANN

A model was trained for a maximum of 150 epochs. To mitigate the risk of overfitting, early stopping based on validation loss was employed, with training halted if no improvement was observed over 10 consecutive epochs. The ReLU activation function was used for all hidden layers, while the output layer utilized a linear activation function to accommodate the regression nature of the task. The Adam optimizer was adopted for model training, and a range of learning rates and batch sizes was explored to identify the optimal hyperparameter configuration. We observed that validation loss was increasing rapidly, so we tried to prevent overfitting by adding dropout by 0.1 layers to hidden layers. We determined the best batch size to be 64.

Table 5 summarizes the average localization error, ME, and SD according to the performance achieved by the model with respect to various hidden layer configurations of the model. In the table, the hidden layer neuron numbers giving the lowest average error are shown in bold. Thus, the number of neurons in the hidden layer of the ANN model were 256, 256, 128, and 64, respectively. In the output layer, 2 neurons were used for latitude and longitude. Using the hyperparameters mentioned above, the ANN model achieves an average positioning error of 332 m on the test dataset.

5) XG-BOOST

We performed the XG-Boost model to estimate the location of the device. We applied grid search to achieve the highest performance from the model and identify the optimal hyperparameters. We explored the model's learning rate, the maximum number of iterations (number of estimators), and the maximum tree depth parameters. For each value, we trained the model and evaluated its performance using the R^2 score. The parameters that achieved the best R^2 score were selected to train our final model. To avoid overfitting and reduce training time, we applied the early stopping mechanism based on validation data. The results for the XG-Boost model are presented in Table 6.

The bolded R^2 scores in the table represent the highest performance achieved. As shown in the table, for each number of estimators, a maximum depth of 10-12 and learning rates of 0.05 and 0.1 resulted in optimal performance. These parameters directly affect the model's learning and generalization capabilities. A higher number of estimators generally leads to better performance, but it may also increase the risk of overfitting. Conversely, fewer estimators allow the model to train and test faster. The max depth parameter defines the maximum depth of each tree in the model; as depth increases, the model becomes more complex, which can again lead to overfitting. The learning rate determines the contribution of each tree to the final prediction: Smaller

TABLE 5. Average localization error of ANN models under various numbers of neurons at the hidden layers.

Number of Neurons at the Hidden Layer	Mean Error	Median Error	Standard Deviation
256, 128, 64	341 m	231 m	384 m
256, 128, 64, 32	345 m	234 m	386 m
256, 256, 128, 64	332 m	218 m	384 m
512, 256	353 m	237 m	380 m
512, 256, 128	339 m	228 m	384 m
512, 256, 128, 64	336 m	223 m	386 m
512, 256, 256	334 m	217 m	380 m
512, 256, 256, 128	338 m	225 m	389 m
512, 256, 256, 128, 64	338 m	224 m	387 m
512, 256, 256, 64	338 m	223 m	384 m
1024, 512, 128	338 m	228 m	385 m
1024, 512, 256, 128	343 m	227 m	386 m
1024, 512, 256, 64	333 m	219 m	384 m

values result in slower but more stable learning. Taking into account all these aspects, the optimal parameters for the XG-Boost model were determined as a number of 400 estimators, a maximum depth of 12, and a learning rate of 0.05 with the R^2 score of 0.9214. The XG-Boost model, trained with the optimal parameters, achieved an average localization error of 327.66 meters on the test dataset.

6) LIGHTGBM

We developed two separate LightGBM models, one for predicting latitude, LightGBM-LAT, and the other for predicting longitude, LightGBM-LON. To select the optimal parameters for the LightGBM model, we applied a grid search and chose the parameters of the model that achieved the highest R^2 score. Table 7 and Table 8 present the performances of the LightGBM-LAT and LightGBM-LON models in terms of the R^2 score according to the various values of the parameters, respectively.

We obtained the best parameters for two models as follows: the number of leaves, learning rate, and the numbers of estimators are 400, 0.02, and 1000, respectively. Also, other parameters such as subsample, colsample bytree, reg alpha, reg lamda, and random state are settled to 0.8, 0.8, 0.1, 0.1, and 42, respectively.

LightGBM-LAT and LightGBM-LON models achieved R^2 scores of 0.9505 and 0.8962, respectively. By combining the outputs of both models, y_{lat} and y_{lon} , the average localization error under the optimal parameter configuration

TABLE 6. R^2 scores of XG-Boost models for different parameter settings.

		Learning rate			
		0.01	0.05	0.1	0.2
number of estimator = 200					
Max	6	0.8132	0.9082	0.9135	0.9165
	8	0.8465	0.9167	0.9194	0.9196
Depth	10	0.8631	0.9202	0.9214	0.9209
	12	0.8730	0.9212	0.9214	0.9206
number of estimator = 400					
Max	6	0.8879	0.9136	0.9166	0.9177
	8	0.9051	0.9193	0.9205	0.9196
Depth	10	0.9131	0.9215	0.9214	0.9209
	12	0.9165	0.9214	0.9214	0.9206
number of estimator = 600					
Max	6	0.9009	0.9157	0.9176	0.9177
	8	0.9129	0.9203	0.9207	0.9196
Depth	10	0.9181	0.9216	0.9214	0.9209
	12	0.9200	0.9214	0.9214	0.9206
number of estimator = 800					
Max	6	0.9055	0.9168	0.9176	0.9177
	8	0.9153	0.9203	0.9207	0.9196
Depth	10	0.9194	0.9216	0.9214	0.9209
	12	0.9208	0.9214	0.9214	0.9206

is reduced to 325.43 meters, demonstrating the effectiveness of the ensemble learning.

7) HYBRID MODEL

To enhance localization performance by combining the strengths of Deep Learning and tree-based methods, we designed a hybrid regression model integrating CNN feature extraction with XGBoost regression. The CNN takes feature vectors derived as input and is trained to capture meaningful patterns from these features. After training, the learned feature representations from the CNN are used as inputs for the XGBoost model to predict the device's latitude and longitude. Notably, for optimizing the best hyperparameters of both the CNN and XGBoost models, only the RSSI values were used as inputs.

The CNN architecture employed consists of two one-dimensional convolutional layers with 32 and 64 filters, respectively, each followed by ReLU activation functions.

TABLE 7. R^2 score of LightGBM-LAT according to different parameters.

		Learning rate			
		0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
number of estimator = 600					
Number of Leaves	200	0.9499	0.9503	0.9501	0.9496
	400	0.9501	0.9503	0.9501	0.9497
	600	0.9500	0.9501	0.9499	0.9495
number of estimator = 800					
Number of Leaves	200	0.9502	0.9504	0.9501	0.9496
	400	0.9504	0.9503	0.9501	0.9497
	600	0.9502	0.9501	0.9499	0.9495
number of estimator = 1000					
Number of Leaves	200	0.9504	0.9504	0.9501	0.9496
	400	0.9503	0.9505	0.9501	0.9497
	600	0.9502	0.9501	0.9499	0.9495

TABLE 8. R^2 scores of LightGBM-LON model for different parameters.

		Learning rate			
		0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
number of estimator = 600					
Number of Leaves	200	0.8947	0.8960	0.8959	0.8954
	400	0.8954	0.8959	0.8960	0.8951
	600	0.8953	0.8957	0.8955	0.8949
number of estimator = 800					
Number of Leaves	200	0.8954	0.8961	0.8959	0.8954
	400	0.8961	0.8959	0.8960	0.8951
	600	0.8953	0.8957	0.8955	0.8949
number of estimator = 1000					
Number of Leaves	200	0.8957	0.8961	0.8959	0.8954
	400	0.8959	0.8962	0.8960	0.8951
	600	0.8953	0.8957	0.8955	0.8949

The convolutional feature maps are then flattened and passed through a fully connected dense layer of 64 neurons with ReLU activation, before the final output layer predicts the latitude and longitude coordinates with a linear activation function. The model was trained for 100 epochs with a batch

size of 32 using the Adam optimizer and mean squared error loss.

For the XGBoost regression models predicting latitude and longitude independently, we selected 400 estimators, a maximum tree depth of 12, and a learning rate of 0.09. These hyperparameters were obtained via grid search and demonstrated robust performance in the localization task.

This hybrid approach aims to integrate the powerful feature learning capability of CNNs with the interpretability and strong predictive performance of gradient-boosted trees. The results of the Hybrid Model for each FV configuration are presented in Table 10 and Table 11, illustrating its performance across different input representations.

B. AVERAGE POSITIONING ERROR ACCORDING TO DIFFERENT FEATURE VECTORS

In this section, we present the performance of benchmarking ML models based on different sets of features. To investigate the impact of various characteristics of the LoRa link on localization performance, a series of feature vectors were constructed by augmenting the baseline FV, which initially included only RSSI, with additional features. Then, for each resulting input configuration (dataset), Machine Learning models were trained using the optimal hyperparameters identified in Section V-A, and the localization error was evaluated on the test set.

Table 9 summarizes the set of FV used in our experiments, indicating the combination of input features included in each. The following abbreviations are used: CH - Channel, CNT - Counter, AT - Airtime.

Table 10 presents the mean localization error (in meters) corresponding to different feature combinations involving SF, channel, counter, and airtime. Table 11, in particular, highlights the effect of incorporating SNR and ESP (Estimated Signal Power) alongside RSSI, and while also illustrating the influence of channel, counter, and airtime features on mean localization error.

Table 10 presents the mean localization error (in meters) from the test data, based on the use of different characteristics of the LoRa link. FV 1 utilizes only the RSSI feature. FV 2 combines RSSI with the SF feature. Feature Vectors 3, 4, and 5 represent combinations of RSSI and SF with the channel, counter, and airtime features, respectively. FV 6 incorporates RSSI and SF alongside and counter, while FV 7 includes RSSI, SF, channel, counter, and airtime. Finally, FV 8 is formed by combining RSSI, SF, counter, and airtime features to construct the input vector for the model.

Experimental results presented in Table 10 demonstrate that including the SF feature consistently contributes to improved performance when combined with the RSSI feature across all models, resulting in a reduction in the average localization error. In contrast, the inclusion of channel information reduces localization error in the ANN model but has negligible impact on XG-Boost and LightGBM, and slightly increases the error for k -NN, CNN, and SVR.

TABLE 9. Summary of feature vectors and their included features.

Feature Vector (FV) #	Included Features
FV 1	RSSI
FV 2	RSSI, SF
FV 3	RSSI, SF, CH
FV 4	RSSI, SF, CNT
FV 5	RSSI, SF, AT
FV 6	RSSI, SF, CH, CNT
FV 7	RSSI, SF, CH, CNT, AT
FV 8	RSSI, SF, CNT, AT
FV 9	RSSI, SNR
FV 10	RSSI, ESP
FV 11	RSSI, SF, SNR
FV 12	RSSI, SF, ESP
FV 13	RSSI, SF, SNR, ESP
FV 14	RSSI, SF, SNR, ESP, CH
FV 15	RSSI, SF, SNR, ESP, CNT
FV 16	RSSI, SF, SNR, ESP, CNT, AT

Incorporating additional information into the feature set by including the frame counter can help reduce localization error across models. This feature provides valuable insight into the packet reception rate, which may vary depending on location. Such variation reflects differences in signal propagation conditions across locations, influenced by factors such as spatial constraints—for example, the distance between a transceiver and a LoRa gateway. Moreover, other features also contribute to error reduction when combined with RSSI and SF.

Additionally, the proposed Hybrid Model outperforms all other models across most Feature Vectors, achieving the lowest average localization error of **244.51 m** with FV 4. This demonstrates the benefit of combining temporal feature extraction via CNN with the regression capability of XGBoost. The Hybrid Model shows consistent improvements, particularly when richer feature sets are used, as seen across FV 4 to 8. These results confirm that architectural innovations can effectively enhance localization accuracy.

Table 11 presents the average localization error observed in the study, which investigates the potential improvement in positioning accuracy when SNR and ESP are used in conjunction with RSSI across various Feature Vectors. FV 9 and 10 combine RSSI with SNR and ESP, respectively. Vectors 11 and 12 extend RSSI and SF with SNR and ESP. FV 13 integrates RSSI, SF, SNR, and ESP. Vectors 14 and 15 further include channel and counter, respectively. Finally, FV 16 includes RSSI, SF, SNR, ESP, counter, and airtime.

In Table 11, we observed that FV 9 and 10—which incorporate SNR and ESP alongside RSSI—demonstrate an impact on the localization performance of the machine learning models. While SNR and ESP contribute similarly to the performance of k -NN, XGBoost, and LightGBM models, the ESP feature is observed to be more influential in improving the localization accuracy of ANN and CNN models. However, SNR appears to have a negative effect on the performance of SVR and CNN models. Moreover, when RSSI is used with SF, SNR, ESP, channel, and counter features, the inclusion of channel information provides only a minor improvement in localization accuracy. However, the counter feature significantly reduces the positioning error.

The proposed Hybrid Model demonstrates competitive and consistent performance across these extended feature sets. Although it does not always achieve the lowest error in every case, the Hybrid Model maintains robust localization accuracy, particularly with richer feature vectors. For example, with FV 15 and 16, the Hybrid Model achieves errors of 254.30 m and 255.07 m, respectively, close to the best-performing models in those categories. This indicates the hybrid approach’s ability to effectively leverage combined deep and handcrafted features for reliable localization.

When we look at the general performances of the ML models by evaluating Table 10 and Table 11 together, the most effective positioning performance for the SVR and XGBoost models is provided by FV number 4. In contrast, FV number 15 yields the best results for k -NN and CNN, while FV number 16 is optimal for ANN and LightGBM. The proposed Hybrid Model consistently demonstrates strong and competitive performance across these feature vectors, often achieving the lowest or near-lowest localization errors. Notably, it attains the best overall error with FV 4 and maintains robust accuracy with FV 15 and 16. This demonstrates the Hybrid Model’s strength in combining learned and handcrafted features for improved localization.

C. LOCALIZATION ACCURACY

We calculated localization accuracy as the success rate in determining the actual location (ground truth) of the devices. The proximity of each predicted location to the true device location was measured, and a Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) plot was used to illustrate how closely the ML models approximated the real positions. Since CDF is a function that shows the probability that a random variable does not exceed a certain value, it allows the models to show their localization accuracy as a certain percentage. Moreover, in calculating localization accuracy, we utilized feature vectors that demonstrated the best performance across the machine learning models. Figure 3 illustrates the CDF plot of localization errors with probability values. As shown in the figure, the maximum localization error observed across the models can reach up to approximately 4800 meters. However, in general, it can be stated that each model is capable of localizing the device within a 2000 meter with a probability of 99%. A more detailed examination of the

TABLE 10. Average localization error of ML models according to different LoRaWAN message features.

Machine Learning Models	LoRaWAN message features							
	Feature Vector 1	Feature Vector 2	Feature Vector 3	Feature Vector 4	Feature Vector 5	Feature Vector 6	Feature Vector 7	Feature Vector 8
k -NN	338.56 m	326.26 m	332.62 m	291.49 m	329.08 m	305.10 m	309.06 m	295.08 m
CNN	343.88 m	341.39 m	342.55 m	321.71 m	344.02 m	321.71 m	335.78 m	322.83 m
SVR	331.92 m	321.93 m	327.01 m	320.90 m	322.91 m	325.89 m	326.69 m	321.49 m
ANN	332.74 m	329.84 m	319.83 m	315.33 m	318.26 m	303.47 m	305.95	307.46
XG-Boost	327.66 m	318.95 m	318.92 m	248.72 m	318.95 m	250.43 m	251.43 m	249.40 m
Light GBM	325.43 m	316.59 m	315.09 m	252.82 m	315.95 m	254.58 m	255.37 m	251.49 m
Hybrid Model	323.38 m	314.21 m	316.49 m	244.51 m	312.24 m	248.32 m	248.85 m	246.87 m

TABLE 11. Average localization error of ML models according to different LoRaWAN message features.

Machine Learning Models	LoRaWAN message features							
	Feature Vector 9	Feature Vector 10	Feature Vector 11	Feature Vector 12	Feature Vector 13	Feature Vector 14	Feature Vector 15	Feature Vector 16
k -NN	316.01 m	317.72 m	311.58 m	312.48 m	308.87 m	308.69 m	284.58 m	285.65 m
CNN	345.15 m	337.45 m	333.53 m	330.63 m	334.38 m	347.72 m	319.57 m	320.65 m
SVR	409.42 m	433.84 m	403.33 m	428.56 m	396.91 m	396.69 m	395.30 m	395.15 m
ANN	308.19 m	310.86 m	303.60 m	302.66 m	307.77 m	300.29 m	285.74 m	279.66 m
XG-Boost	313.64 m	313.38 m	308.82 m	308.65 m	309.30 m	308.87 m	249.77 m	251.05 m
Light GBM	311.54 m	311.49 m	307.17 m	305.89 m	306.32 m	305.79 m	250.17 m	249.57 m
Hybrid Model	311.72 m	306.61 m	308.27 m	303.12 m	309.85 m	308.67 m	254.30 m	255.07 m

region in the figure corresponding to localization errors up to 300 meters reveals that approximately 60% to 70% of the predictions made by each model fall within this error margin.

The Table 12 presents a more detailed percentage probability that a model can predict a location within a specified localization error threshold. The maximum localization error thresholds are defined in the table as 50, 100, 150, 200, 250, and 300 meters, consistent with the values presented in Figure 3. As shown in the table, the proposed models are able to estimate device locations within a 250 meter error margin with a probability ranging from 54% to 66%. Among them, the Hybrid Model achieves the highest accuracy, predicting locations within this threshold with a 72% probability. Furthermore, both LightGBM and XGBoost models reach over 71% accuracy within a 300 meter range, underscoring their strong performance for LoRa network localization tasks.

Overall, the Hybrid Model consistently provides the best or comparable localization accuracy probabilities across all thresholds, demonstrating the effectiveness of integrating

DL-based feature extraction with gradient boosting regression for enhanced positioning precision.

D. LOCATION ESTIMATION ERROR

In addition, we quantify the localization error by calculating the Euclidean distance (in meters) between the predicted device location obtained from the ML models and Hybrid Model and the corresponding ground truth position. Localization errors are presented and compared with errors reported in previous studies using the same dataset and comparable ML approaches.

Table 13 presents the localization error in meters in terms of MSE, ME, and SD, comparing the results of our ML models with those of previous studies that used the same dataset. Previous utilizing the LPWAN dataset has mostly focused on models such as SVR, ANN, k -NN, and RF, our work extends this by evaluating XGBoost, LightGBM, CNN, and a Hybrid Model. When comparing the SVR model, we used the RBF kernel, applied feature selection, and performed

FIGURE 3. Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) plot of probability of localization accuracy.

TABLE 12. Localization accuracy probabilities.

ML Models	Maximum Localization Error					
	50 m	100 m	150 m	200 m	250 m	300 m
<i>k</i> -NN	33%	41%	48%	55%	61%	66%
CNN	3%	25%	40%	47%	54%	61%
SVR	15%	35%	43%	40%	57%	63%
ANN	28%	37%	45%	53%	60%	66%
XG Boost	32%	42%	50%	58%	65%	71%
Light GBM	32%	41%	50%	59%	65%	71%
Hybrid Model	34%	44%	52%	60%	66%	72%

an extensive hyperparameter search using grid and random search methods to optimize the model. As a result, the average localization error significantly decreased from 1148 meters which is obtained in study [44] to 320 meters, yielding an improvement of approximately 73%. For the *k*-NN model, we compared our results with previous studies [32], [43], [44], where the lowest reported average positioning error was 313.26 meters. Our improved implementation reduced this error to 284.58 meters, corresponding to an improvement of around 10%. In contrast, for the ANN model, our results remained comparable to previous works, with no significant improvement in average localization error observed. These

TABLE 13. Average localization error of ML models comparison of model performance against previous work (N/A - data not available).

Model	Study	MSE	ME	SD
Hybrid Model	This work	244.51 m	130.39 m	337.11 m
	[44]	1148 m	N/A	N/A
XG Boost	This work	248.72 m	145.54 m	326.86 m
	[44]	320.90 m	194.38 m	376.45 m
Light GBM	This work	249.57 m	146.72 m	328.14 m
	[32]	277.61 m	163.49 m	N/A
ANN	This work	279.66 m	171.70 m	350.84 m
	[32]	313.26 m	217.98 m	N/A
<i>k</i> -NN	[43]	398.40 m	273.03 m	N/A
	[44]	343	N/A	N/A
	This work	284.58 m	160.01 m	380.81 m
CNN	This work	319.57 m	219.96 m	352.20 m
RF	[44]	340 m	N/A	N/A
	[37]	735.37 m	N/A	N/A

comparisons were made against existing models commonly used in earlier LoRa localization studies.

In addition, we introduced three new models—Hybrid Model, XGBoost, LightGBM, and CNN—into the evaluation. The performance of the CNN model provides many outputs about the use of CNN in regression problems, the average positioning error does not provide an improvement compared to other models.

Our proposed methods yielded better results than state-of-the-art baselines reported in recent literature, achieving the lowest positioning errors of 244.51 m, 248.72 m, and 249.57 m, respectively.

Although some previous works [37], [44] included the RF model, we did not use it as a baseline in our study because both XGBoost and LightGBM are built upon the fundamental structure of the RF algorithm and are considered to be more advanced ensemble learners.

Importantly, our proposed Hybrid Model further reduces the average localization error to 244 meters, outperforming all other models. This confirms that integrating CNN-based feature extraction with gradient boosting regression enhances localization accuracy in LoRa networks beyond the performance of individual models. All localization error results indicate that we have improved outdoor positioning in LoRa networks by at least 10%, according to existing ML studies in the literature.

Figure 4 presents a spatial heatmap of the average localization error computed within 150×150 m grid cells, based on predictions made by the Hybrid Model. Each cell represents the average error for all samples that fall within the corresponding geographic area. The heatmap shows how the localization error is distributed across space. Although most areas have moderate and relatively stable error levels, some isolated regions show significantly higher errors, up to around 2 km, indicating locations with particularly degraded propagation conditions. In general, 42.6% of the grid cells have an average error below 350 m, 33% below 300 m, and 21.7% below 250 m.

E. COMPUTATION TIME

We present the computation times of machine learning models. Computation time is critical, especially in real-time location estimation applications. Especially in wireless networks such as LoRaWAN, low computational cost is essential due to the use of low-power devices. Other types of gateways and other devices in the network have difficulty performing complex calculations. As the computation time increases, the processor load and energy consumption increase. For this reason, fast-running models are vital in applications where IoT and autonomous vehicles are used.

Although we perform offline training and testing of our models, we still consider computation time to be a crucial factor. Given technological advancements and real-life applications, the potential deployment of our models on device localization in the LoRAWAN network or their utilization via cloud computing adds value to our study. Thus, we place future implications of our work in both research and industry and present the computation times of the ML models.

FIGURE 4. Heatmap of the average localization error achieved by the Hybrid Model. Each grid cell corresponds to an area of 150×150 m.

FIGURE 5. Average computation time per test sample (in seconds) for different ML models and the Hybrid Model, along with standard deviation shown as error bars.

The bar graph in Figure 5 illustrates the average computation time along with the corresponding standard deviation for each machine learning model evaluated, providing information on their computational efficiency. The bar graph illustrates the average computation time for each model on the test dataset. For each sample in the test set, the computation time was recorded, followed by the calculation of the mean and standard deviation to assess the computational efficiency of benchmarking models. The average computation times are 0.010593, 0.1490, 0.00614, 0.005203, 0.05685, 0.00096, 0.00116, 0.001296, and 0.3004 seconds for *k*-NN, CNN, SVR-LAT, SVR-LON, ANN, XGBoost, LightGBM-LAT, LightGBM-LON, and Hybrid Model. For the SVR model, the computation time of the SVR-LAT model was used as the reference, while for the LightGBM model, the computation time of the LightGBM-LON model was used. However, for the Hybrid Model, the computation time of the CNN and the computation time of the XGboost model were added, and an overall average computation time for the model was presented. The standard deviations of computation times are 0.00560, 0.0186, 0.000475, 0.01047, 0.00047, 0.00052, 0.0153. The LightGBM and XGBoost models demonstrate

substantially faster inference times, with computation times as low as around 1 ms. This efficiency notably improves the practicality and responsiveness of the application in real-life scenarios.

The Hybrid Model has the highest computation cost (0.30 s), whereas LightGBM and XGBoost offer significantly lower times (0.001 s). This analysis highlights the trade-off between model complexity and computational efficiency, which is critical for real-time and low-power IoT applications. Such performance makes them ideal candidates for deployment in real-time applications, particularly in resource-constrained environments like IoT and LoRaWAN networks. This emphasizes the trade-off between accuracy and efficiency, and the importance of selecting models that align with the computational capabilities of target deployment systems.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to investigate and improve the performance of Machine Learning algorithms for outdoor localization based on LoRa signals. We performed seven ML models as follows: k -NN, CNN, SVR, ANN, XG-Boost, LightGBM, and a Hybrid Model, which integrates CNN for spatio-temporal feature extraction with XG-Boost for robust regression. This model aims to combine the strengths of Deep Learning and Gradient Boosting techniques. We used the open-source LoRaWAN dataset, which reflects large-scale deployment in various urban and rural areas and is one of the most widely used datasets in the literature for benchmarking localization methods. Our analysis provided a comprehensive exploration of various LoRa signal characteristics and their impact on the positioning accuracy of the ML models.

The results demonstrated that LightGBM and XG-Boost models outperformed with approximately 249 meter localization error, especially in scenarios when RSSI is used in conjunction with other features. The proposed Hybrid Model further improved the localization performance, achieving the lowest error of approximately 244 meters, thus outperforming all baseline models. Our models can locate incoming signals within 300 meters with a probability of 60% to 70% and within 250 meters with an average probability of 60%. Additionally, the Hybrid Model achieved the highest probability (72%) of predicting locations within 300 meters, indicating its superior accuracy and robustness. Moreover, LightGBM and XG-Boost have faster computation time than other models, which could be significant in real-time outdoor positioning, where computational efficiency plays a key role. While the Hybrid Model slightly increases the computation time compared to XG-Boost, it provides improved accuracy, presenting a favorable trade-off for applications where precision is more critical.

Our main contributions to the state of the art are demonstrating the performance of ML models in outdoor positioning for LoRa networks, presenting comparative computational times of Machine Learning models, reducing localization error, and improving localization accuracy by at

least 10% compared to previous existing studies, and comprehensively examining the impact of various characteristics on positioning accuracy. The introduction of a CNN-XGBoost hybrid architecture represents a novel contribution that enhances both model robustness and accuracy.

Further research could explore the integration of other signal processing techniques or include modifications to the FV to improve localization performance further. There is also potential to investigate alternative Machine Learning models and to optimize the methods in terms of computational efficiency. Moreover, further study could be extended to include stress testing, with particular emphasis on scenarios involving limited data availability, such as a reduced number of gateways or severely degraded link characteristics (e.g., RSSI) in worst-case conditions, to assess the model's robustness and generalization capabilities.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

ANN	Artificial Neural Network.
AoA	Angle of Arrival.
AT	Airtime.
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy.
CH	Channel.
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network.
CNT	Counter.
DR	Data Rate.
ESP	Estimated Signal Power.
FV	Feature Vector.
GD	Gradient Descent.
GPS	Global Positioning System.
IoT	Internet of Things.
ISM	Industrial, Scientific and Medical.
KNN	K-Nearest Neighbors.
LAT	Latitude (Geographical Coordinate).
LightGBM	Light Gradient Boosting Machine.
LightGBM-LAT	LightGBM model trained for Latitude prediction.
LightGBM-LON	LightGBM model trained for Longitude prediction.
LON	Longitude (Geographical Coordinate).
LoRa	Long Range.
LoRaWAN	Long Range Wide Area Network.
LoS	Line-of-Sight.
LPWAN	Low Power Wide Area Network.
MAE	Mean Absolute Error.
MLE	Maximum Likelihood Estimation.
ML	Machine Learning.
MIoTY	Massive Internet of Things.
MLP	Multilayer Perceptron.
MSE	Mean Squared Error.
N/A	Not Available.
NB-IoT	Narrowband Internet of Things.

NLoS	Non-Line-of-Sight.
PDR	Packet Delivery Ratio.
PER	Packet Error Rate.
RF	Radio Frequency.
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error.
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator.
RTP	Real Time Plot.
RTT	Round Trip Time.
SF	Spreading Factor.
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio.
SVR	Support Vector Regression.
SVR-LAT	SVR model trained for Latitude prediction.
SVR-LON	SVR model trained for Longitude prediction.
TDMA	Time Division Multiple Access.
TDoA	Time Difference of Arrival.
TiSCH	Time Slotted Channel Hopping.
ToA	Time of Arrival.
TSCH	Time Slotted Channel Hopping.
TTS	Transmission Time per Symbol.
Wi-SUN	Wireless Smart Ubiquitous Network.
XGBoost	Extreme Gradient Boosting.

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NUR KELEŞOĞLU received the B.Sc. and M.Sc. degrees in electrical and electronics engineering from Yasar University, Izmir, Türkiye, in 2020 and January 2023, respectively. She is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree with the Institute of Theoretical and Applied Informatics (ITAI), Polish Academy of Sciences (PAS), Gliwice, Poland. She is a Research Assistant with ITAI, PAS. Her senior design project, "Artificial Intelligence Enabled Position Tracking and Prediction of Mobile IoT Devices in a Smart Factory Environment," was supported by the 2209-B Program of the Turkish Scientific and Technological Research Council (TÜBİTAK). She was a part-time Teaching Assistant with Yasar University. Her thesis was based on the sample-based regularization support vector regression (SR-SVR) and its application for fire detection. Her current research interests include machine learning applications for engineering problems, data analysis, indoor positioning, wireless networks, smart homes, and the IoT.

MARZENA HALAMA received the M.Sc. degree in applied mathematics from the Silesian University of Technology, where her thesis focused on the design and deployment of lightweight CNNs for mobile platforms with constrained computational resources. She is currently a Research Assistant with the Institute of Theoretical and Applied Informatics (ITAI), Polish Academy of Sciences (PAS). She has previous experience as a Programmer, a Software QA Specialist, and a University Lecturer in the basics of AI. Her Ph.D. research focuses on NLP, LLMs, and transformers, with an emphasis on optimization, fine-tuning, and evaluation of language models. She is leading a research project on advanced NLP and human-robot interaction (HRI) that integrates speech processing with real-time visual perception and SLAM. Her technical experience includes DL algorithm implementation, data pre-processing and analysis, and computer vision.

ANNA STRZODA received the M.S. degree in mathematics from the Silesian University of Technology, Gliwice, Poland, in 2019, and the Ph.D. degree from the Institute of Theoretical and Applied Informatics (ITAI), Polish Academy of Sciences (PAS), in 2025. She is currently a Researcher with the Internet of Things Group, ITAI, PAS. Her scientific interests are focused on the application of metaheuristics and optimization methods in wireless networks, the IoT, and smart city applications. Her research concentrates on the performance evaluation of LPWAN-particularly LoRa, indoor localization using BLE, UWB, and MEMS signal processing. She is a Finalist in the National Student Nobel Prize Competition in the category of technical sciences. In 2023, she was awarded as a Laureate of the International School of Pioneers Program, organized by the Polish Development Fund, for building a startup.